

1 **How to construct and validate an Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index:**
2 **Implementation at regional scale in urban areas prone to flash flooding**

3 **Estefanía Aroca-Jiménez^{a,*}, José María Bodoque^a, Juan Antonio García^b**

4 ^a Department of Mining and Geological Engineering, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Carlos
5 III, Toledo, 45071, Spain

6 ^b Department of Business Administration, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Real Fábrica de
7 Sedas, Talavera de la Reina, 45600, Spain

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9 * Corresponding author. E-mail address: estefania.aroca@uclm.es (E. Aroca-Jiménez)

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11 **HIGHLIGHTS**

- 12 • An Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI) has been constructed and validated.
- 13 • ISEVI's construction followed an integrated approach, considering vulnerability components
14 and dimensions.
- 15 • Uncertainty analysis shows the stability of the different categories of the ISEVI.
- 16 • Sensitivity analysis notes which vulnerability factors causes greater variability in ISEVI scores.
- 17 • Spatial patterns of vulnerability are identified, which may help decision makers to develop
18 tailored mitigation strategies.

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22 **ABSTRACT**

23 Flash flooding is the natural hazard provoking the largest number of casualties, so adequately
 24 characterizing vulnerability is key to improve flood risk analysis and management. Developing
 25 composite indices is the most widely used methodology in vulnerability analysis. However, very few
 26 studies have so far assessed vulnerability in urban areas prone to flash flooding and the resulting
 27 research presents two main drawbacks: i) a fragmented approach is often pursued, i.e. without jointly
 28 considering the vulnerability components (exposure, sensitivity and resilience) and the two most
 29 influential dimensions in urban environments (social and economic); and ii) vulnerability indices are not
 30 usually validated because an ancillary dataset is not generally available and flash flooding events do not
 31 happen simultaneously in all urban areas of a particular region. Considering the above gaps, this paper
 32 describes the construction of an Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI) at the regional
 33 scale, which considers all vulnerability components and social and economic dimensions. ISEVI was

34 subsequently validated through an uncertainty and sensitivity analysis using the Monte Carlo method.
35 Further, regional spatial patterns of vulnerability were identified implementing a Latent Class Cluster
36 Analysis. Uncertainty analysis reveals the high stability of vulnerability categories of the ISEVI and
37 sensitivity analysis shows that the type and the conservation state of buildings are the vulnerability
38 factors that cause a greater variability in ISEVI scores. The method deployed here may allow specific
39 strategies for vulnerability reduction to be developed based on disaggregating the validated ISEVI into
40 dimensions and components and using the regional spatial patterns characterized.

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42 Keywords

43 Integrated analysis, Flash flooding, Internal validation, Uncertainty, Sensitivity analysis, Spatial patterns

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58 **1 Introduction**

59 Floods are the most dangerous natural hazard worldwide, causing the largest losses both in terms
60 of human lives (Milanesi et al., 2015) and economic damage in urban environments (Highfield and
61 Brody, 2013). In particular, flash floods are considered the type of flood that generate the greatest risk in
62 respect of loss of life since they are triggered very quickly, i.e. usually within a few hours of the onset of
63 heavy rainfall (Marchi et al., 2010). This significantly limits the response time of the population at risk
64 and the emergency authorities, which increases the potential impact and hampers flood risk management
65 (Terti et al., 2015).

66 Despite the efforts made over the past decades to reduce flood impacts, associated losses are still
67 rising mainly due to the increase in exposure and global climate change (Koks et al., 2015; Han et al.,
68 2020). Until the beginning of the 21th century, risk management was primarily based on applying
69 structural measures, such as the construction of dams or levees (Cardona et al., 2012; Highfield and
70 Brody, 2013; Ahmad et al., 2020). However, the implementation of such measures has not proven to be
71 entirely effective in reducing flood risk. In some cases, they can even have the opposite effect due to the
72 levee effect or safe development paradox (Haer et al., 2020). Moreover, structural flood risk
73 management measures usually require a large financial investment and may have considerable negative
74 impacts on the natural environment due to river-floodplain disconnection (Highfield and Brody, 2013).
75 In this context, the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction through the International Strategy for
76 Disaster Risk Reduction and derived frameworks, such as the Sendai Framework 2015-2030 currently in
77 force (UNISDR, 2015), highlights the need to consider hazard and vulnerability jointly throughout the
78 risk analysis and management process. This is intended to minimize risk while increasing preparedness
79 for response and recover (UNISDR, 2015; Bakkensen et al., 2017; Mohammed, 2019).

80 In response to the need to improve risk management and adaptation strategies, academics and
81 practitioners have conducted numerous studies to better understand vulnerability in urban environments
82 (Bakkensen et al., 2017). Nevertheless, both the terminology and methodology used in vulnerability

83 assessment is still a subject of discussion within the scientific community (Adger et al., 2004; Willis and
84 Fitton, 2016; Bera et al., 2019). Vulnerability is an inherent characteristic of the social system at risk,
85 which does not only depend on its location or on the nature of the hazard that generates the risk (Cutter
86 et al., 2008; Oulahen et al., 2015; Nazeer and Bork, 2019). Therefore, vulnerability is also a function of
87 exposure (i.e., people and assets at risk), sensitivity (i.e., the level of impact on people and assets at
88 risk), and resilience (i.e., the ability of the social system to resist, absorb, cope with, adapt, and recover
89 from such impact; Cutter et al., 2008; Diaz-Sarachaga and Jato-Espino, 2019). Additionally, to
90 comprehensively characterize vulnerability in urban environments, its three components (i.e., exposure,
91 sensitivity and resilience) in addition to the most influential dimensions (i.e., social and economic) must
92 all be considered (Bera et al., 2019; Diaz-Sarachaga and Jato-Espino, 2019).

93 The most widely used methodology to analyze vulnerability so far is the development of
94 composite-indices (i.e., the compilation of multi-thematic individual indicators into a single value),
95 which allows an abstract concept that cannot be directly measured to be quantified (Willis and Fitton,
96 2016; Bakkensen et al., 2017; Anderson et al., 2019). This approach allows managers and policymakers
97 to integrate vulnerability outcomes into risk assessment and management (Kontokosta and Malik, 2018).
98 Numerous vulnerability analyses have been published to date in different scientific areas, such as
99 climate change (Adger et al., 2004), natural disasters (Cutter et al., 2008) and social-ecological systems
100 (Estoque and Murayama, 2014). In the field of natural disasters, vulnerability has been assessed for
101 natural hazards in general (Cardona and Carreño, 2011; Kontokosta and Malik, 2018), and for specific
102 natural hazards such as floods (Shaw et al., 2014; Oulahen et al., 2015; Nazeer and Bork, 2019), coastal
103 hazards (Peacock et al., 2010; Cai et al., 2016), hurricanes (Davidson and Lambert, 2001; Flanagan et
104 al., 2011), earthquakes (Asadzadeh et al., 2015) and droughts (Mildrexler et al., 2016). In spite of the
105 abundant literature available, vulnerability is still usually addressed in a fragmented way, i.e. it does not
106 consider all of the components (Cutter et al., 2008; Kontokosta and Malik, 2018) or dimensions (Fekete,
107 2009; Cardona and Carreño, 2011; Andrade and Szlafsztein, 2018).

108 In the case of flash flooding, the number of vulnerability-related published papers is much more
109 limited. Most papers looking at flash flooding tackle vulnerability analysis in a one-dimensional way,
110 characterizing only physical vulnerability (Papathoma-Köhle, 2016; Milanesi et al., 2018; Papathoma-
111 Köhle et al., 2019), social vulnerability (Terti et al., 2015; Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2017; Andrade and
112 Szlafsztein, 2018; Rodríguez-Gaviria et al., 2019), or economic vulnerability (Aroca-Jiménez et al.,
113 2018). Conversely, those studies that consider more than one dimension do not usually integrate the
114 different vulnerability components (Guillard-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Nahiduzzaman et al., 2015;
115 Karagiorgos et al., 2016a, 2016b; Rahman et al., 2016). To overcome these constraints, it is necessary to
116 develop integrated and multidimensional approaches to truly understand the roots of vulnerability and,
117 therefore, to improve risk management (Cardona et al., 2012).

118 To date, very few attempts have been made to validate vulnerability index outcomes (Tate, 2012;
119 Bakkensen et al., 2017). The most widely used approach so far is based on the use of independent proxy
120 data referring to real observable outcomes, such as emergency service requests (Kontokosta and Malik,
121 2018), mortality (Adger et al., 2004; Gall, 2007; Peacock et al., 2010; Cardozo and Monteiro, 2019),
122 building damage or losses (Peacock et al., 2010; Papathoma-Köhle, 2016; Papathoma-Köhle et al.,
123 2019; Rufat et al., 2019), number of disasters (Cutter et al., 2003; Debortoli et al., 2017), post-event
124 surveys (Fekete, 2009; Sherrieb et al., 2010) and qualitative information from focus groups (Oulahen et
125 al., 2015). In other cases, validation is addressed by comparing results with other reference indices
126 (Gall, 2007; Peacock et al., 2010; Sherrieb et al., 2010; Estoque and Murayama, 2014). The approaches
127 described above are included in what is known as external validation, and they are usually implemented
128 when natural hazard impacts happen at regional or national scale (e.g. hurricanes, earthquakes or
129 riverine flooding). However, these approaches are very difficult to implement in flash flood-prone areas,
130 especially if the vulnerability index to be validated is regional or national. This is because the required
131 data are not normally available (Fekete, 2009) and because flash flooding events are not simultaneously
132 triggered in all urban areas of interest. Thus, an increasingly being used alternative is to validate
133 vulnerability indices internally through an analysis of how changes in index inputs affect modeled

134 results (Gall, 2007; Tate, 2012, 2013). Internal validation is usually performed by means of a sensitivity
135 and uncertainty analysis, Monte Carlo simulations being the most frequently used approach (Davidson
136 and Lambert, 2001; Gall, 2007; Tate, 2012, 2013), although other statistical tools such as correlation
137 and regression analysis and cross-validation have also been employed (Schmidtlein et al., 2008; Cai et
138 al., 2016; Anderson et al., 2019; Marzi et al., 2019; Nazeer and Bork, 2019).

139 Therefore, the goal of this paper is to construct and validate at regional scale an Integrated Socio-
140 Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI) in urban areas prone to flash flooding. It considers all
141 vulnerability components (i.e., exposure, sensitivity and resilience) and it takes into account two of the
142 most influential dimensions in the urban environment (i.e., social and economic dimensions). To do this,
143 a set of social and economic variables were statistically analyzed through the sequential application of a
144 Hierarchical Segmentation Analysis and a Principal Component Analysis to extract vulnerability factors.
145 Subsequently, ISEVI was internally validated by analyzing sensitivity and uncertainty through the
146 implementation of the Monte Carlo method. Finally, a Latent Class Cluster Analysis was applied to
147 identify vulnerability spatial patterns within the study region, which enabled specific management
148 strategies to be proposed for each cluster of urban areas.

149 The paper is divided into five sections. Section 2 describes the procedure followed for the
150 identification of urban areas affected by flash flooding within the study region and the different statistical
151 tools implemented in the construction and validation of the ISEVI and in the identification of
152 vulnerability spatial patterns. The results from these statistical analyses, including the identification of
153 vulnerability factors and the spatial heterogeneity of ISEVI scores, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis,
154 and the spatial representation of different clusters of urban areas identified and their profiles are
155 presented in Section 3. Section 4 discusses the different strengths and limitations of the paper, compares
156 the results with those obtained in other published papers and highlights the potential improvements that
157 the work can make to flash flood risk management. Finally, Section 5 outlines the conclusions of this
158 work.

160 **2 Methodology**

161 Fig. 1 illustrates the followed research methodology by showing the different statistical tools and
162 steps involved.

164 **Figure 1.** Flowchart showing the research methodology followed in this work. Blue boxes depict
165 intermediate information, white boxes represent statistical techniques, and red boxes show final results.

167 **2.1 Study area and identification of urban areas affected by flash flooding**

168 Castilla y León is the largest autonomous region in Spain (94,226 km²) and it is located in the
169 northwest of the country (Fig. 2). Its relief mainly consists of a large elevated plateau (700-1,100
170 m.a.s.l.) surrounded by large mountain ranges that can reach heights of up to 2,600 m.a.s.l. Compared to
171 the plateau, where annual rainfall ranges from 400 to 600 mm, the steep mountain slopes cause an
172 increase of rainfall in the periphery, where 1,000-1,500 mm can be exceeded. In these peripheral areas,
173 high intensity rainfall events can occur, which can trigger flash flooding due to their geomorphological
174 configuration (Ruiz-Villanueva et al., 2010; Bodoque et al., 2015).

175 Castilla y León has a population of slightly more than 2.4 million, although this figure has been
176 decreasing over the last few decades. Of the 2,248 municipalities into which Castilla y León is divided,
177 95% of them have less than 2,000 inhabitants. The average population density of these municipalities is
178 7 inhabitants per km², which is far lower than the mean for the region (i.e., 26 inhabitants per km²) and
179 for the country (i.e., 92 inhabitants per km²). These urban areas have an inverted population pyramid,
180 where the population over 65 years accounts for 36% of the total population (i.e., ageing population).
181 Regarding the economic context, the average GDP per capita of the region (i.e., €23,447) is below the
182 average GDP of the whole of Spain (i.e., €24,970), although the figure for rural areas is even lower (i.e.,
183 €16,641; INE, 2016). The high ageing index together with the depopulation process in these urban areas,
184 which is mainly caused by the lack of job opportunities (Martínez and Delgado, 2013), means that they
185 face a real challenge in the future, especially as regards the maintenance of infrastructures and services
186 (CES, 2018).

187 In order to identify urban areas prone to flash flooding, some requirements were considered.
188 First, urban areas that were crossed by rivers with a longitudinal slope higher than or equal to 0.01m/m
189 were selected, i.e., this threshold is usually considered to classify a stream as mountainous (Bodoque et
190 al., 2015). Subsequently, it was verified that the urban areas selected were in turn affected by rivers
191 catalogued as Areas with Significant Potential Risk of Flooding (ARPSIs) and by flood-prone areas with
192 low or exceptional probability (i.e., 500-year return period). Both layers (i.e., ARPSIS and 500-year
193 flood-prone areas) are consistent with the provision of the Directive 2007/60/CE on flood risk

194 assessment and management. 39 urban areas met the specifications above and, accordingly, were
195 considered in the vulnerability analysis (Fig. 2).

196

197

198 **Figure 2.** Location of the study region (Castilla y León, Spain). Flash-flood prone urban areas
199 (represented in soft yellow) are the result of crossing river longitudinal slopes ($\geq 0.01\text{m/m}$),
200 ARPSIs and 500-year flood layers.

201

202 2.2 Seeking vulnerability drivers: identification of vulnerability indicators

203 A total of 189 variables were initially characterized, 71 associated with the social dimension and
204 118 with the economic dimension of vulnerability. These variables were: i) extracted directly from
205 public databases at local, regional or national level (e.g., population, education or unemployment); ii)
206 estimated from spatial information or secondary variables (e.g., collective vulnerability, infrastructures
207 or per capita incomes); or iii) expressly requested from competent authorities (e.g., dependency or
208 health services). Variables were then standardized using the z-score method and those considered
209 redundant (i.e., absolute correlation coefficient above or equal to 0.9) were eliminated (Schmidtlein et
210 al., 2008; Bera et al., 2019;), so the original set of variables was reduced to 55 for the social dimension

211 and 31 for the economic dimension (see Table S1 and Table S2 in Appendix A Supplementary data). To
212 overcome the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) inherent sample size limitation (Nardo et al., 2008),
213 a Hierarchical Segmentation Analysis (HSA) was previously implemented. HAS is a multivariate
214 statistical technique that allows original variables to be divided into groups according to the distance or
215 similarity between them (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014). The graphical output of the HSA (i.e., dendrogram)
216 helped to determine the optimal number of groups into which vulnerability variables can be divided,
217 subsequently applying a PCA in each of them. PCA allowed to reduce the number of variables by
218 linearly combining them, resulting in the so-called principal components or factors (Sarstedt and Mooi,
219 2014).

220

221 2.3 Construction of the Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI)

222 Factor scores associated with each urban area were expressed as the standard deviation of the
223 mean of each factor, which were obtained from the PCA. Factors were associated to the different
224 vulnerability components according to the type of variables they included. Those urban areas with a
225 positive factor score in a factor associated with exposure or sensitivity components were more
226 vulnerable than the mean, while those urban areas with a negative factor score in a factor associated
227 with exposure or sensitivity components were less vulnerable than the mean. Regarding the resilience
228 component, those urban areas with a positive factor score were more resilient than the mean and those
229 urban areas with a negative factor score were less resilient. Each vulnerability component (i.e.,
230 exposure, sensitivity and resilience) considered both social and economic vulnerability dimensions,
231 which in turn were composed of their respective vulnerability factors. Thus, an index called Integrated
232 Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI) was calculated for each urban area using Eq. (1):

$$233 \quad ISEVI = Exposure + Sensitivity - Resilience \quad (1)$$

234 Vulnerability components considered both vulnerability dimensions (i.e., social and economic),
235 so the ISEVI equation can be expressed as Eq. (2):

$$ISEVI = (Soc\ Exp + Ec\ Exp) + (Soc\ Sens + Ec\ Sens) - (Soc\ Res + Ec\ Res) \quad (2)$$

Where the *Soc* prefix is related to the social dimension and the *Ec* prefix to the economic dimension, *Exp* is exposure, *Sens* is sensitivity, and *Res* is resilience. Each vulnerability component by dimension (i.e., social or economic exposure, social or economic sensitivity, and social or economic resilience) was calculated using Eq. (3):

$$V_{CD} = \frac{\sum_{f=1}^n (w_f \cdot S_f)}{\sum_{f=1}^n w_f} \quad (2)$$

Where V_{CD} is the vulnerability of a certain component by dimension, w_f is the weight of the n factor, and S_f are the factor scores of the n factor. The weighting of each vulnerability factor was determined by using the tolerance statistic (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014). Thus, a high tolerance value meant that a factor was poorly correlated with the other vulnerability factors, so it had a higher weight allocated in the ISEVI. On the contrary, a low tolerance value meant that a factor was more correlated with the rest of vulnerability factors, so it had a lower weight allocated in the ISEVI. ISEVI scores were represented using the quintiles method, where categories coincide with the 20th, 40th, 60th, and 80th percentiles of the ISEVI values (Tate, 2013; Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2018).

2.4 Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis: Monte Carlo simulation

Uncertainty analysis enabled the stability of vulnerability categories allocated to the urban areas to be assessed. Sensitivity analysis decomposed uncertainty to determine the influence of vulnerability index inputs (i.e., vulnerability factors) on the different outputs, i.e., ISEVI, component and dimension values (Tate, 2013). To address both uncertainty and sensitivity analysis, the Monte Carlo method was implemented. To do this, we first fitted scores of each factor to a probability distribution function, assuming that factor scores were uncensored data. The Anderson-Darling A^2 statistic was used to decide which distribution best fitted the factor scores of each vulnerability factor. Smaller values of the A^2 statistic tend to indicate better fitting distributions, i.e., $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ in the goodness-of-fit test (Yap and

260 Sim, 2011). Therefore, each original vulnerability factor was characterized by the different parameters
261 of the fitted distribution functions, which constituted the input to the Monte Carlo analysis, generating
262 samplings randomly. Vulnerability factor weights were introduced as triangular distributions, where the
263 minimum weight corresponded to the lower limit, the median to the center, and the maximum weight to
264 the upper limit. Concerning the output of the Monte Carlo analysis, the influence of the different
265 vulnerability factors on ISEVI values was analyzed. Thus, ISEVI was considered as an output function,
266 which was calculated according to Eq. 2. Based on the different inputs (i.e., vulnerability factors) and
267 the output function (i.e., ISEVI calculation), 21,504 simulations were undertaken.

268 Further, the influence of the different vulnerability factors on component and dimension scores
269 was assessed, which required the definition of an output function for each component and dimension
270 considered. Those outputs (i.e., social and economic exposure, social and economic sensitivity, and
271 social and economic resilience) were calculated considering only the necessary factors in each case. For
272 instance, to define social exposure, only the factors that characterized the exposure within the social
273 dimension were considered. Weights were again introduced as triangular distributions, but the necessary
274 parameters (i.e., upper limit, center, and lower limit) were recalculated in each case considering only the
275 factors of the component or dimension to be defined. The influence of the vulnerability factors on the
276 different components by dimensions were computed using Eqs. 2 and 3. On the basis of the different
277 inputs (i.e., vulnerability factors) and output functions (i.e., vulnerability components by dimension),
278 5,120 Monte Carlo simulations were performed for social and economic exposure, economic sensitivity,
279 and social resilience; 7,168 simulations for social sensitivity; and 4,096 simulations for economic
280 resilience.

281 Of the different statistics provided by the Monte Carlo analysis, the median was used here to
282 validate the ISEVI (Tate, 2012, 2013). Thus, the difference or bias between the median of the fitted
283 probability distribution for each vulnerability factor and the original factor scores was calculated. The
284 total bias for each urban area was the sum of all these differences. To validate the original vulnerability
285 categories and therefore the original ISEVI values, the ISEVI was recalculated considering the median

286 of the fitted probability distributions (i.e., instead of the original factor scores). Accordingly, we
287 estimated as many new ISEVI values as vulnerability factors were originally identified for each urban
288 area. The percentage of cases in which vulnerability would change category for each urban area was
289 calculated.

290 Finally, the sensitivity tornado plot helped to identify the influence of the different index inputs
291 (i.e., vulnerability factors) on vulnerability characterization (i.e., ISEVI and component by dimension
292 scores). To estimate the variation ranges caused by the different index inputs on the index outputs,
293 values associated with the 5% and 95% percentiles of the fitted probability distributions were
294 considered. Vulnerability factors located at the top of the sensitivity tornado plot were those that had the
295 greatest influence on the ISEVI and component by dimension scores. Conversely, the inputs located at
296 the bottom of the sensitivity tornado plot were those that had the least influence.

297

298 2.5 Seeking spatial patterns of vulnerability

299 In order to identify possible spatial patterns of vulnerability on a regional scale, a Latent Class
300 Cluster Analysis (LCCA) was conducted, which allowed heterogeneity within a set of urban areas to be
301 identified by dividing them into groups with similar characteristics (Vermunt and Magidson, 2016). To
302 do this, a categorical latent variable was created and the probability that each urban area belonged to a
303 certain group was computed, which depended on factor scores of the vulnerability factors identified.
304 Five different models were assessed, progressively considering from where there was no sample
305 heterogeneity (i.e., all urban areas belonged to the same group) to where there was sample heterogeneity
306 with five spatial patterns (i.e., five different clusters of urban areas). The minimum value of the
307 Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) helped to determine the optimal number of clusters, which
308 weights the fit and the parsimony of a model (Vermunt and Magidson, 2016). The estimation of the
309 model parameters and the statistical tests associated with them provided information on which
310 vulnerability factors were not relevant (i.e., not statistically significant) to be ascertained in the division

311 of urban areas into clusters (i.e., $p\text{-value} > 0.05$). The model profile indicated the class-specific marginal
312 means, which allowed us to identify the vulnerability sources for each cluster.

313 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) or Welch tests were performed in order to verify whether the
314 differences in ISEVI and component by dimension scores between the different clusters identified were
315 statistically significant. First, the assumption of homogeneity of variances (or homoscedasticity) was
316 checked using Levene's test. If the significance value of this test was above 0.05, then a one-way
317 ANOVA was undertaken; otherwise, a robust test of equality of means (i.e., Welch test) was performed.
318 Both tests (i.e., ANOVA and Welch tests) enabled whether there were statistically significant
319 differences between the cluster means to be ascertained. So, if the significance value of the
320 aforementioned tests was above 0.05, it could be concluded that there were no differences. However, if
321 the significance value was below 0.05, then differences between the cluster means were established.
322 Post-hoc tests (i.e., the Honestly-Significant-Difference Tukey test was associated with one-way
323 ANOVA and the Games-Howell test was paired with the Welch test) indicated which clusters of urban
324 areas were different according to their ISEVI or component values (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014).

325

326 **3 Results**

327 3.1 Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI)

328 A total of 19 vulnerability factors were identified, 11 concerning the social dimension and 8
329 related to the economic dimension (Table 1). Exposure was characterized by 6 vulnerability factors, 3
330 from the social dimension and 3 from the economic dimension. Of these, the one that had the highest
331 weight in the ISEVI was the factor 'urban environment' (7.7%), which was related to households and
332 infrastructures located in flood-prone areas. Sensitivity was characterized by 8 vulnerability factors, 5
333 from the social dimension and 3 from the economic dimension. Among these, the one that had the
334 highest weight in the ISEVI was the factor 'vehicle fleet' (11.3%), which was associated with the
335 number of vehicles and their preservation. Finally, resilience was characterized by 5 vulnerability

336 factors, 3 from the social dimension and 2 from the economic dimension. The one with the highest
 337 weight in the ISEVI was the factor ‘constructive resilience’ (11.6%), which was related to the
 338 conservation condition of households. Regarding the weight of vulnerability components by dimension,
 339 social sensitivity was the one with the highest percentage (25.0%), while social exposure was the one
 340 with the smallest value (5.6%). The vulnerability component with the highest weight in the ISEVI was
 341 sensitivity (42.1%), followed by resilience (35.4%), and, lastly, exposure (22.6%). Vulnerability factors
 342 that characterize the social dimension accounted for 53.4% of the ISEVI, while vulnerability factors that
 343 characterize the economic dimension explained 46.6%.

344

345 **Table 1.** Vulnerability factors identified in the PCA. Parenthesis percentages correspond to the different
 346 weights allocated to each element in ISEVI construction.

Variable	Factor	Component by dimension	Component
Total population	Total Social Exposure	Social Exposure	Exposure
Health centers	(0.7%)	(5.6%)	(22.6%)
Hospital beds			
Medical staff			
Kindergartens			
Elementary schools			
Secondary schools			
Retirement homes			
Tourist accommodation			
Population per settlement area	Exposure in the Urban Built-up		
Vacant households	Environment		
Underground built-up area	(2.4%)		
Permanent households			
Households with 1 storey above ground level and/or another storey below ground level	Constructive Exposure		
Households with 2 or more storeys above ground level	(2.4%)		
Number of dwellings located at flood-prone areas	Urban environment	Economic Exposure	
Length of the streets (meters) located at flood-prone areas	(7.7%)	(17.0%)	
Electrical transformers located at flood-prone areas			
Parks and gardens (m ²) located at flood-prone areas			
Education infrastructures (kindergartens, elementary and secondary schools) located at flood-prone areas	Municipal infrastructures and facilities		
Retirement homes located at flood-prone areas	(7.4%)		
Bridges located at flood-prone areas			
Protections of riverbanks (linear meters) located at flood-prone areas	Potentially floodable dwellings		
Secondary houses	(1.9%)		
Dwellings with 1 storey above ground level			
Dwellings with 1 or more storeys below ground level			
Inhabitants aged 0-4	Youth Social Sensitivity	Social Sensitivity	Sensitivity
Inhabitants aged 5-14	(4.7%)	(25.0%)	(42.1%)
Population projection aged 0-4 for 2025			
Population projection aged 5-14 for 2025			
Unemployment rates	Labour Social Sensitivity		
Long-term unemployed people	(3.8%)		
Households where any unemployed people live			
Inhabitants aged 65 or older	Social Sensitivity due to Dependency		
Population projection aged 65 or older for 2025	(2.2%)		
Dependency rates: males			
Dependency rates: females			
Households where people aged 65 or older live			

Illiterate people			
Distance to the nearest hospital	Social Hospital Sensitivity		
Travel time to the nearest hospital	(6.0%)		
Distance to the nearest health center	Social Health Sensitivity		
Travel time to the nearest health center	(8.3%)		
Number of workers in agricultural sector	Potential job losses	Economic Sensitivity	
Number of workers in industry, construction and services sectors	(0.9%)	(17.1%)	
Tourist accommodation capacity			
Unemployment rate	Economic situation of municipalities		
Municipal debt per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	(4.9%)		
Replacement costs (€/m ²) of dwellings located at flood-prone areas	Vehicle fleet		
Mean age of the vehicle fleet	(11.3%)		
Vehicle fleet			
Households in good condition	Constructive Resilience	Social Resilience	Resilience
Households in poor condition	(11.6%)	(22.9%)	(35.4%)
Inhabitants aged 15-64	Mature Social Resilience		
Population projection aged 15-64 for 2025	(2.6%)		
Fixed investments per inhabitant	Economic Resilience due to Investments		
Municipal available budget per capita	(8.8%)		
Tax base of the property tax (thousands of €)	Economic situation of households	Economic Resilience	
Per capita income (€/inhab.)	(3.7%)	(12.5%)	
Main houses			
Fixed investments per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	Municipal investments		
Municipal budget per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	(8.8%)		

347

348 Five vulnerability categories were considered: i) very high; ii) high; iii) medium; iv) low; and v)

349 very low (Fig. 3). ISEVI values range from -0.74 (i.e., the lowest vulnerability) to 0.48 (i.e., the highest

350 vulnerability). The most vulnerable urban areas are in the northeast and northwest of the region, and the

351 least vulnerable urban areas are in the east and northeast of the region. The bar chart associated with

352 each urban area shows the ISEVI score disaggregated by vulnerability component. So, the left bar

353 represents the score in exposure, the middle bar the score in sensitivity, and the right bar the score in

354 resilience. Bar height is directly proportional to component scores. Bar direction indicates the sign of

355 component scores, which can be positive (i.e., value above the mean) or negative (i.e., value below the

356 mean). To make map understanding intuitive, red is associated with *very high* category and dark green

357 with *very low* category in the exposure and sensitivity components, while colors are inverted in the

358 resilience component (i.e., red is associated with *very low* category and dark green with *very high*

359 category). Urban areas with a very high vulnerability usually have very high exposure and sensitivity

360 and very low resilience. However, not all combinations of the component values are the same. The

361 exposure component has a smaller variation range than sensitivity and resilience components, i.e.,

362 exposure can vary from very high to high categories, while sensitivity can vary from very high to low

363 categories and resilience from high to very low categories. On the other hand, urban areas with very low

364 vulnerability usually have very low exposure and sensitivity and very high resilience, but there is great
365 variability in the combinations (i.e., exposure can vary from high to very low categories; sensitivity
366 from very high to very low categories; and resilience from very high to low categories).

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368

369 **Figure 3.** ISEVI values for each urban area and its decomposition into vulnerability component scores.

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371 Similarly, scores of the different vulnerability components disaggregated by dimension were
372 represented using the quintiles method (Fig. 4). In this case, the bar chart associated with each urban
373 area displays component values disaggregated by vulnerability dimension. The left bar represents the
374 score in the social dimension and the right bar represents the score in the economic dimension. Bar
375 height and direction follow the same representation scheme as the one described for Fig. 3. Urban areas
376 with the highest values of exposure are mainly located in the northwest of the region, and the lowest

377 values are mainly located in the northeast. Urban areas with the highest values of sensitivity are mainly
378 located in the northeast of the region, while the lowest values are mainly located in the east. Finally,
379 urban areas with the highest and the lowest values of resilience are in the northeast of the region. Those
380 urban areas with the highest exposure values tend to have a very high or high economic exposure, while
381 social exposure has a greater variability (i.e., it can vary from very high to low categories). Furthermore,
382 urban areas with the lowest exposure values tend to have both very low social and economic exposure.
383 Regarding sensitivity, urban areas with the highest values usually have very high values of both social
384 and economic sensitivity, although both can vary from very high and medium categories in the different
385 combinations. In contrast, urban areas with the lowest sensitivity values have a very low economic
386 sensitivity, but social sensitivity can vary from medium to very low categories. Finally, urban areas with
387 the highest resilience values do not have a clear dominance of any category (i.e., there is not a clear
388 mode in the categories frequency), where social resilience can vary from very high to medium
389 categories and economic resilience from very high to low categories. Conversely, urban areas with the
390 lowest resilience values tend to have very low social resilience, but in the case of economic resilience
391 the variation range is very large (i.e., categories can vary from very high to very low).

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395 **Figure 4.** Vulnerability component scores and their disaggregation by vulnerability dimension

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3.2 Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis

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ISEVI scores depicted in Fig. 3 represent the baseline index scores. Fig. 5 shows the total bias (i.e., the sum of all the differences between the median of the fitted probability distribution for each vulnerability factor and the original factor scores) obtained in Monte Carlo simulation for each urban area using the quantile classification method with 3 categories: high, moderate, and low. Red shows those urban areas where total bias is positive, i.e., most of the original factor scores are higher (more vulnerable) than the median of the fitted vulnerability factor distributions. Meanwhile, green shows urban areas with a negative total bias, i.e., most of the original factor scores are lower (less vulnerable) than the median of the fitted vulnerability factor distributions. Color intensity reflects the absolute total bias values, so lighter colors are associated with smaller biases (i.e., more robust ISEVI values) and dark colors with higher biases (i.e., less robust ISEVI values). Moreover, original vulnerability categories are indicated for each urban area: VH (very high), H (high), M (medium), L (low), and VL (very low). The above means that urban areas with a higher positive total bias usually have a very high or high vulnerability, while urban areas with a higher negative total bias tend to have a very low vulnerability.

412

413 **Figure 5.** Bias of the ISEVI values in comparison with the median values obtained from Monte Carlo
 414 simulation

415

416 If the bias of each vulnerability factor is considered separately instead of the total bias, it is
 417 possible to ascertain how the vulnerability category associated with each urban area would change by
 418 considering the median of fitted probability distributions for each vulnerability factor (i.e., rather than
 419 the original factor scores). Thus, Fig. 6 shows the original ISEVI values (i.e., baseline index scores) for
 420 each urban area and, associated with each one of them, a pie chart showing the percentage of cases in
 421 which, when considering the median of the fitted probability distributions, there would be an upgrade of
 422 the vulnerability category (i.e., dark blue), a degrade of the vulnerability category (i.e., light blue), and
 423 where vulnerability category would not change (i.e., grey). Only 6 of the 39 urban areas would not
 424 change vulnerability category in any case (i.e., 100% percentage). Of these, only one has a very high
 425 vulnerability, two have a low vulnerability, and three have a very low vulnerability. Urban areas in

426 which the percentage of upgrading the vulnerability category is predominant (i.e., only 3 of 39) show a
 427 medium, low and very low vulnerability associated. No urban area would degrade the vulnerability
 428 category (i.e., the percentage is not prevalent in any case). Of the urban areas in which the percentage of
 429 not varying the vulnerability category exceeds the rest (i.e., 30 of 39), 6 of them have a very high
 430 vulnerability, 8 a high vulnerability, 7 a medium vulnerability, 5 a low vulnerability, and 4 a very low
 431 vulnerability. Therefore, in 36 of the 39 urban areas there would not be a change in the vulnerability
 432 category, which represents 92% of the total.

433

434

435 **Figure 6.** Vulnerability uncertainty: changes in vulnerability categories

436

437 Fig. 7 shows the influence of vulnerability factors obtained on ISEVI values. Sensitivity tornado
 438 plot orders, from top to bottom, those elements that have a higher influence on the output function. The
 439 bar size is directly proportional to the variation range caused by each input element on the output
 440 variable. The vulnerability factor that has the greatest influence on the ISEVI values is ‘constructive

441 resilience’, which explains 6.6% of the total range of variability of ISEVI scores. Conversely,
 442 vulnerability factors that have the least influence on the ISEVI values are ‘economic resilience due to
 443 investments’ and ‘municipal investments’, which explain 2.9%.

444

445

446 **Figure 7.** Sensitivity tornado plot showing the influence of vulnerability factors on ISEVI values. Y axis
 447 indicates the variation range of each factor is indicated next to each one as a percentage. X axis shows
 448 the variability range of the ISEVI scores. Orange and blue bars correspond to the result of the output
 449 variable if 5% and 95% percentiles of the input variable were considered, respectively.

450

451 Since ISEVI considers social and economic dimensions as well as vulnerability components, the
 452 influence of vulnerability factors on the different components by vulnerability dimension was also
 453 assessed (Fig. 8). Regarding social exposure, the vulnerability factor that has the greatest influence is
 454 ‘exposure in the urban built-up environment’ (i.e., explaining the 36.9% of the variation range), while
 455 the vulnerability factor that has the greatest influence on economic exposure is ‘potentially floodable
 456 dwellings’ (i.e., 33.1% of the variation range). Regarding sensitivity, the vulnerability factor that has the
 457 greatest influence on social sensitivity is ‘social health sensitivity’ (i.e., explaining the 20.9% of the
 458 variation range), while the vulnerability factor that has the greatest influence on economic sensitivity is

459 'vehicle fleet' (i.e., 35.7% of the variation range). Finally, regarding resilience, the vulnerability factor
 460 that has the greatest influence on social dimension is 'constructive resilience' (i.e., explaining 44.3% of
 461 the variation range), while the factor that has the greatest influence on the economic dimension is
 462 'economic situation of households' (i.e., 56.8% of the variation range).

463

464

465 **Figure 8.** Sensitivity tornado plot showing the influence of vulnerability factors on component scores by
 466 vulnerability dimension. Y axis indicates the variation range of each factor is indicated next to each one
 467 as a percentage. X axis shows the variability ranges of the scores of the different vulnerability
 468 components by dimension. Orange and blue bars correspond to the result of the output variable if 5%
 469 and 95% percentiles of the input variable were considered, respectively.

470

471 3.3 Regional spatial patterns of vulnerability

472 BIC statistic determined that the best model was the one that considered four clusters of urban
473 areas (BIC(LL)=1,795.83). Model parameters indicated that the ‘constructive resilience’ factor was not
474 statistically significant for the division of urban areas into clusters (i.e., $p\text{-value} > 0.05$). Finally, Fig. 9
475 displays the model profile, which shows the cluster to which each urban area belongs (Fig. 9a), and the
476 associated bar plot represents the pattern of the different clusters (Fig. 9b). Bars show the standard
477 deviation of the mean for each factor by dimension and component and for each cluster. Bars direction
478 corresponds to the sign of the standard deviation, which can be positive (i.e., higher exposure,
479 sensitivity and resilience than the cluster mean) or negative (i.e., lower exposure, sensitivity and
480 resilience than the cluster mean).

481 Thus, cluster 1 is composed of 14 urban areas (i.e., 35.5% of the total), and it is characterized by
482 showing the lowest values in all factors of social exposure, and in ‘urban environment’ and ‘potentially
483 floodable dwellings’ factors of economic exposure. With regard to sensitivity, this cluster includes
484 urban areas with the highest values in ‘social sensitivity due to dependency’ and ‘social health
485 sensitivity’ factors of the social dimension. Conversely, these urban areas show the lowest values in
486 ‘youth social sensitivity’ and ‘labor social sensitivity’ factors of the social dimension, and in ‘potential
487 job losses’ and ‘economic situation of municipalities’ factors of the economic dimension. Regarding
488 resilience, urban areas included in this cluster show the highest values in ‘economic resilience due to
489 investments’ factor of the social dimension. Moreover, they show the lowest values in the ‘mature social
490 resilience’ factor of the social dimension and in the ‘economic situation of households’ factor of the
491 economic dimension.

492 Cluster 2 is composed of 11 urban areas (i.e., 28.2% of the total) characterized by showing the
493 highest values in the ‘constructive exposure’ factor of the social dimension, and in the ‘potentially
494 floodable dwellings’ factor of the economic dimension. On the contrary, these urban areas show the
495 lowest values in the ‘urban environment’ and ‘municipal infrastructures and facilities’ factors of the
496 economic dimension.

497 Cluster 3 is composed of 10 urban areas (i.e., 25.7% of the total) depicted by the highest values
498 in the ‘municipal infrastructures and facilities’ factor of the economic dimension. Regarding sensitivity,
499 these urban areas show the highest values in the ‘social hospital sensitivity’ factor of the social
500 dimension, and in the ‘vehicle fleet’ factor of the economic dimension.

501 Finally, cluster 4 is composed of 4 urban areas (i.e., 10.6% of the total) characterized by showing
502 the highest values in the ‘total social exposure’ and ‘exposure in the urban built-up environment’ factors
503 of the social dimension, and in the ‘urban environment’ factor of the economic dimension. With regard
504 to sensitivity, these urban areas present the highest values in ‘youth social sensitivity’ and ‘labor social
505 sensitivity’ factors of the social dimension, and in ‘potential job losses’ and ‘economic situation of
506 municipalities’ factors of the economic dimension. Conversely, they show the lowest values in ‘social
507 sensitivity due to dependency’, ‘social hospital sensitivity’ and ‘social health sensitivity’ factors of the
508 social dimension, and in the ‘vehicle fleet’ factor of the economic dimension. Regarding resilience,
509 these urban areas have the highest values in the ‘mature social resilience’ factor of the social dimension,
510 and in the ‘economic situation of households’ factor of the economic dimension. Conversely, they show
511 the lowest values in the ‘economic resilience due to investments’ factor of the social dimension.

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513

514

515 **Figure 9.** Latent class cluster analysis profile. A: Urban areas division into clusters. B: Characteristics

516 of different spatial patterns identified (model profile), where TSE=‘total social exposure’ factor;

517 EUBUE=‘exposure in the urban built-up environment’ factor; CE=‘constructive exposure’ factor;

518 UE=‘urban environment’ factor; MIF=‘municipal infrastructures and facilities’ factor; PFD=‘potentially

519 floodable dwellings’ factor; YSS=‘youth social sensitivity’ factor; LSS=‘labour social sensitivity’

520 factor; SSD=‘social sensitivity due to dependency’ factor; SHS=‘social hospital sensitivity’ factor;

521 SHhS=‘social health sensitivity’ factor; PJL=‘potential job losses’ factor; ESM=‘economic situation of

522 municipalities’ factor; VF=‘vehicle fleet’ factor; MSR=‘mature social resilience’ factor; ERI=‘economic

523 resilience due to investments’ factor; and ESH=‘economic situation of households’ factor.

After obtaining the results of the LCCA, it was verified that there were statistically significant differences between ISEVI and component by dimension scores and the different clusters identified. Table 2 contains some basic statistics of the different clusters (i.e., mean and standard deviation) and the ANOVA/Welch test output. Regarding exposure, urban areas included in clusters 2 and 3 have a higher mean than the urban areas included in cluster 1. Moreover, there are differences in exposure values by dimension. Urban areas included in cluster 2 have a higher mean social exposure than the urban areas in cluster 3 and these, in turn, have a higher mean than those listed in cluster 1. In terms of economic exposure, urban areas contained in cluster 3 have a higher mean than those featured in cluster 1. Finally, urban areas included in cluster 3 have a higher mean ISEVI value than those embedded in cluster 1. Statistically significant differences were not found in the rest of components or vulnerability dimensions.

Table 2. ANOVA/Welch test output: descriptive statistics, homogeneity of variances (Levene’s test), equality of means (ANOVA and Welch tests) and post-hoc tests (multiple comparisons).

Component	Dimension	Cluster 1		Cluster 2		Cluster 3		Cluster 4		Levene’s test		ANOVA/Welch test		Post hoc test: Tukey HSD/Games-Howell test (p-value<0.05)
		M	Sd	M	Sd	M	Sd	M	Sd	F	p-value	F	p-value	
Exposure	Social	-0,56	0,19	0,58	0,77	-0,19	0,17	0,82	0,74	8,23	0,00	15,02 ^a	0,00	Cluster 2 > Cluster 3, Cluster 1 Cluster 3 > Cluster 1 Cluster 3 > Cluster 1 Cluster 2, Cluster 3 > Cluster 1
	Economic	-0,43	0,26	-0,27	0,19	0,60	0,90	0,75	1,18	10,80	0,00	4,92 ^a	0,02	
	Total	-0,46	0,22	-0,06	0,31	0,40	0,68	0,77	1,01	7,00	0,00	8,49 ^a	0,00	
Sensitivity	Social	-0,04	0,47	0,11	0,38	0,08	0,31	-0,37	0,24	1,33	0,28	1,65	0,20	Cluster 2, Cluster 3 > Cluster 1
	Economic	-0,04	0,91	0,05	0,55	0,13	0,65	-0,32	0,77	1,01	0,40	0,39	0,76	
	Total	-0,04	0,40	0,09	0,33	0,10	0,42	-0,35	0,27	0,78	0,51	1,62	0,20	
Resilience	Social	0,10	0,56	-0,10	0,59	-0,12	0,45	0,23	0,26	0,95	0,43	0,77	0,52	Cluster 3 > Cluster 1
	Economic	0,19	1,09	-0,25	0,33	-0,06	0,17	0,19	0,21	2,25	0,10	0,96	0,42	
	Total	0,13	0,65	-0,16	0,47	-0,10	0,30	0,22	0,21	0,75	0,53	1,08	0,37	
ISEVI		-0,17	0,26	0,08	0,20	0,17	0,28	-0,05	0,30	0,42	0,74	3,80	0,02	Cluster 3 > Cluster 1

Notes: M (mean); Sd (standard deviation); a (asymptotically F distributed)

4 Discussion

This paper analyzes vulnerability at the regional scale of urban areas prone to flash flooding. An Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI) was constructed considering all vulnerability components (i.e., exposure, sensitivity and resilience) and two of the most influential vulnerability dimensions in the urban environment, i.e. social and economic (Diaz-Sarachaga and Jato-Espino, 2019).

546 The ISEVI was subsequently validated through an uncertainty and sensitivity analysis, which was
547 performed using the Monte Carlo method.

548 Since there is no consensus within the scientific community on how best to address a
549 vulnerability analysis, numerous methodological approaches have been employed so far. The
550 development of indicator-based assessments is currently the most widely used methodology (Anderson
551 et al., 2019; Bera et al., 2019). Many works have constructed these indicators from data they have
552 collected through expert or population surveys, but such methods are very costly and time consuming,
553 especially if they have to be implemented in large areas (Andrade and Szlafsztain, 2018). In urban areas
554 prone to flash flooding, the typical limited data availability is another shortcoming to be considered. In
555 this context, using statistical information gathered from public-access databases, as deployed here, is a
556 more feasible alternative to construct vulnerability indices, enabling a higher number of variables to be
557 evaluated. Monitoring index values is also possible, since these databases are periodically updated,
558 which allows temporal and spatial vulnerability dynamics to be characterized (Fekete, 2012; Cai et al.,
559 2016; Bakkensen et al., 2017; Marzi et al., 2019). The selection of variables is the most important step
560 of the index construction (Bera et al., 2019). Not only should those characteristics that explain
561 vulnerability in other papers already published be noted, but also those variables related to the specific
562 socio-economic context, where the vulnerability analysis is being conducted, as vulnerability is place-
563 specific (Cutter, 1996; Adger et al., 2004; Oulahen et al., 2015; Anderson et al., 2019). However, in this
564 approach variables selection procedure is generally conditioned by the limited data availability and low
565 updating frequency, as usually occurs in areas prone to flash flooding (Willis and Fitton, 2016; Cortès et
566 al., 2018; Rodríguez-Gaviria et al., 2019). Data availability also constrains the analysis because not all
567 the desired variables are generated or available at local level, which is the minimum scale at which risk
568 management strategies and policies should be defined (Frazier et al., 2013; Marzi et al., 2019).

569 Regarding the conceptual framework, very few papers have assessed vulnerability associated
570 with flash flooding and they usually follow fragmented approaches, in which the three vulnerability
571 components are not customarily considered. Typically, vulnerability analysis only includes the physical

572 dimension (Papathoma-Köhle, 2016; Milanese et al., 2018; Papathoma-Köhle et al., 2019), the social
573 dimension (Guillard-Gonçalves et al., 2015), or social and physical dimensions jointly (Nahiduzzaman
574 et al., 2015; Karagiorgos et al., 2016a, 2016b; Rahman et al., 2016). Additionally, in those publications
575 where vulnerability components are considered, only the social dimension is taken into account
576 (Debortoli et al., 2017; Andrade and Szlafsztain, 2018; Rodríguez-Gaviria et al., 2019). The
577 aforementioned papers often include some economic variables, but in a very small number compared to
578 the set of variables that characterize the social dimension. Consequently, it is difficult to correctly
579 represent the specific socio-economic context and, hence, the spatial heterogeneity of vulnerability
580 (Frazier et al., 2014; Marzi et al., 2019). Accordingly, the primary knowledge gap to highlight is the
581 lack of research focused on the construction of vulnerability indices that jointly consider vulnerability
582 components and the social and economic dimensions.

583 The use of integrated approaches is key in order to identify the causes of vulnerability, as the
584 index results are obtained and represented graphically disaggregated by components and dimensions.
585 Based on the results obtained here, the most vulnerable urban areas show the highest values of exposure
586 and sensitivity and the lowest values of resilience, which coincides with the findings obtained by
587 Andrade and Szlafsztain (2018). Furthermore, we identified that the highest values of exposure are
588 mainly due to the economic dimension, i.e. related to households, collective buildings and urban
589 infrastructures located in flood-prone areas, which is inherent to densely populated places, as stated by
590 Rahman et al. (2016) and Rodríguez-Gaviria et al. (2019). As far as sensitivity is concerned, the highest
591 values are controlled by both the social and economic dimensions. The social dimension is mainly
592 characterized by areas with an ageing population (i.e., high dependency rates) and limited access to
593 health services. Concerning the economic dimension, it includes areas with high unemployment rates,
594 high municipal debt and an old vehicle fleet. These characteristics are common to urban areas prone to
595 flash flooding, i.e. mountainous areas where ageing and retired people live and where employment
596 opportunities are almost nonexistent, being this finding in accordance with those published by Guillard-
597 Gonçalves et al. (2015), Karagiorgos et al. (2016b), and Rahman et al. (2016). Regarding the resilience

598 component, the lowest values are driven by the social dimension, mainly marked by the poor condition
599 of buildings and the limited economic capacity of families, as other papers also highlighted
600 (Karagiorgos, Thaler, Heiser, et al., 2016; Rahman et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Gaviria et al., 2019).
601 Therefore, integrated analysis allows the different sources of vulnerability to be identified, which can
602 help involved decision-makers to develop specific vulnerability reduction strategies in order to improve
603 flood risk management (Schauser et al., 2010; Cardona et al., 2012).

604 Vulnerability analyses usually end with the graphical representation and explanation of index
605 results, but very few studies try to validate it (Tate, 2013; Bakkensen et al., 2017). A lack of index
606 validation can cause decisions made by risk managers and planners concerning the development of
607 vulnerability reduction strategies to be questioned (Tate, 2013). One of the most widely used
608 methodologies to validate vulnerability indices is based on the use of an alternative database related to
609 natural disaster outcomes, such as the number of calls to emergency services, number of deaths or extent
610 of damage to buildings (Peacock et al., 2010; Debortoli et al., 2017; Kontokosta and Malik, 2018;
611 Cardozo and Monteiro, 2019; Rufat et al., 2019). However, this approach is very difficult to implement
612 in urban areas affected by flash flooding because the availability of an ancillary dataset with which to
613 perform index validation is usually restricted in mountainous areas (Fekete, 2009; Cortès et al., 2018).
614 Moreover, the ISEVI was developed at regional scale and flash flooding events are triggered locally.
615 This means that flash flooding can occur in one of the urban areas included in the vulnerability analysis,
616 but a flash flooding event is not simultaneous triggered in the 39 urban areas considered. Therefore,
617 using alternative databases such as those described above to validate regional vulnerability indices
618 related to flash flooding would not be conceptually appropriate (Bakkensen et al., 2017; Marzi et al.,
619 2019).

620 An increasingly used methodological alternative is to internally validate the vulnerability index
621 through an uncertainty and sensitivity analysis, which has been the approach deployed here. This does
622 not substitute for external validation, but certainly is an indicator that the index is robust to some
623 variability in the input data (Nardo et al., 2008; Schmidtlein et al., 2008; Tate, 2012). Here, variation

624 sources included in the sensitivity analysis were vulnerability factor scores and their weights. Some
625 authors argue that the optimal option is to assign equal weights to all factors (Guillard-Gonçalves et al.,
626 2015; Karagiorgos et al., 2016a; Rahman et al., 2016). However, as there may be a correlation between
627 the different vulnerability factors, this weighting method can lead to an overrepresentation of certain
628 characteristics (Tate, 2013). Establishing weights based on the tolerance statistic can help to mitigate
629 this effect (Nardo et al., 2008; Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2017, 2018). Further, the weighting of vulnerability
630 factors is considered one of the most subjective decisions in index construction and one of the most
631 influential in index outcomes (Tate, 2013; Nazeer and Bork, 2019). The above is confirmed here, since
632 weights occupy the third position in the ISEVI-related tornado plot (see Fig. 7). Nevertheless, if results
633 aggregated by components and dimensions are assessed (see Fig. 8), it is observed how weights lose
634 importance and are relegated to the last position in the different tornado plots. Accordingly, ISEVI
635 variability is explained here by vulnerability factors and, hence, by variables included in each
636 vulnerability factor. Thus, the factors on which management strategies should be preferably performed
637 to reduce vulnerability are mainly related to social sensitivity. Accessibility to health infrastructures
638 should thus be improved in those small, more remote urban areas which also have an ageing population
639 with high dependency rates and very limited economic capacity due to the lack of employment.
640 Ultimately, this approach helps to ensure a more optimal allocation of the economic resources available
641 to the municipality for flood risk management, which can be limited in mountainous urban areas
642 (Flanagan et al., 2011; Highfield and Brody, 2013; Kontokosta and Malik, 2018; Rodríguez-Gaviria et
643 al., 2019).

644 The uncertainty analysis relied on comparing ISEVI outcomes with the median of probability
645 distributions of vulnerability factors obtained in the Monte Carlo analysis (Hudrliková, 2013; Tate,
646 2013; Nazeer and Bork, 2019). The median is considered an unbiased estimator of central tendency, as
647 other published works support (Nardo et al., 2008; Hoskins and Mascherini, 2009; Tate, 2012, 2013).
648 Here, we found that those urban areas included in extreme index categories, i.e., very high and very low
649 vulnerability, are those that show the highest deviation from the median (see Fig. 5) and, therefore, the

650 greatest uncertainty, which is in line with other publications (e.g., Tate, 2013). Furthermore, when
651 comparing the categories of vulnerability that would have been obtained if the median of probability
652 distributions of vulnerability factors had been considered instead of the original index scores, it can be
653 seen that most municipalities would not change category (see Fig. 6). This gives an idea of the stability
654 of the ISEVI categories, which can help decision-makers to include ISEVI outcomes in future flood risk
655 management strategies.

656 Regional spatial patterns of vulnerability from LCCA (see Fig.9) can help to develop regional
657 vulnerability reduction strategies tailored to the needs of each urban area cluster (Cai et al., 2016;
658 Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2017, 2018). Thus, urban areas that make up cluster 1 have an elderly population,
659 so they would require a high level of social and economic assistance and better connectivity to the
660 health infrastructure. Dwellings of urban areas included in cluster 2 usually have one or more storeys
661 below ground level, which are the ones that are flooded first, so the implementation of self-protection
662 measures, such as preventing these floors from being used as rest areas, should be encouraged
663 (Karagiorgos et al., 2016b). Urban areas that compose cluster 3 have numerous collective buildings in
664 flood-prone areas, so vulnerability reduction strategies should include evacuation scenarios for which
665 training guided by the emergency services would be necessary (i.e., action drills). It would be essential
666 in these cases to have a map of optimal evacuation routes because these buildings usually concentrate
667 many people and the evacuation process can be critical (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2018). Finally, urban
668 areas included in cluster 4 are the ones with the highest individual and collective exposure and the worst
669 economic situation, so vulnerability reduction strategies should be aimed at promoting mitigation
670 measures at the individual level, such as the development of a system of incentives based on the
671 reduction of local taxes if self-protection measures are implemented (Highfield and Brody, 2013; Aroca-
672 Jiménez et al., 2018). These regional spatial patterns can help to prioritize the actions to be
673 accomplished by competent flood risk management and civil protection authorities. They can also be
674 used to draw up vulnerability reduction strategies and policies to be implemented, which would result in
675 a better allocation of regional resources to flood risk management.

676

677 **5 Conclusions**

678 In this study, an Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI) focusing on urban areas
679 prone to flash flooding has been constructed and validated at the regional level. The use of integrated
680 approaches is essential to identify the different sources of vulnerability, which is achieved by
681 graphically representing the results disaggregated by components and dimensions. The above, in
682 addition to increasing the transparency and objectivity of the index development process, may provide
683 decision-makers with much more intermediate levels of aggregation of the information that can be
684 useful in designing vulnerability reduction strategies. The validation of the ISEVI using the Monte Carlo
685 analysis enabled us to ascertain which index inputs produce a higher variability in the index outcomes
686 and to quantify that variability. This gives an indication of the consistency of the index, which can help
687 decision makers to include the results of the vulnerability index in future flood risk management
688 strategies. The other methodological framework deployed here that can assist in better flood risk
689 management is the identification of spatial patterns of vulnerability from Latent Class Cluster analysis.
690 Such an approach allows vulnerability reduction strategies to be proposed on a regional scale, strategies
691 that are much more closely adapted to the needs of different clusters of urban areas. The above may also
692 help flood risk management and civil protection authorities to prioritize actions to be taken if an
693 emergency situation is declared. It can further lead to a more efficient allocation of regional resources to
694 flood risk management.

695

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703

704 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

705 **Estefanía Aroca Jiménez:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft,
706 Visualization. **José M. Bodoque:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Juan**
707 **A. García:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

708

709 **Declaration of competing interest**

710 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that
711 could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

712

713 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

714 Table S1. Description of the set of social variables used in the construction of the Integrated Socio-
715 Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI; social dimension).

716 Table S2. Description of the set of economic variables used in the construction of the Integrated Socio-
717 Economic Vulnerability Index (ISEVI; economic dimension).

718

719 **Notation**

720 ANOVA = Analysis of Variance

721 Ec Exp = Economic exposure

722 Ec Res = Economic resilience

- 723 Ec Sens = Economic sensitivity
- 724 HAS = Hierarchical Segmentation Analysis
- 725 ISEVI = Integrated Socio-Economic Vulnerability Index
- 726 LCCA = Latent Class Cluster Analysis
- 727 PCA = Principal Component Analysis
- 728 S_f = factor scores of the n vulnerability factor
- 729 Soc Exp = Social exposure
- 730 Soc Res = Social resilience
- 731 Soc Sens = Social sensitivity
- 732 V_{CD} = vulnerability of a vulnerability component by dimension
- 733 w_f = weight of the n vulnerability factor

734

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